

IRIC 2025

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

16–17 SEPTEMBER 2025
IZOLA, SLOVENIA

A preliminary investigation of miswak (*Salvadora persica*) extractives for novel applications

Amina Selmanović^{1,2,3,*}, Wojciech J. Pajerski², Anna Sandak²,
Andreja Kutnar², Rene Herrera Diaz⁴

¹ Faculty of Mathematics, Natural Sciences and Information Technologies, University of Primorska, Glagoljaška 8, 6000 Koper, Slovenia; 89233013@student.upr.si

² InnoRenew CoE, UP IAM, University of Primorska, Titov trg 4, SI-6000 Koper, Slovenia; wojciech.pajerski@innorenew.eu, anna.sandak@innorenew.eu

³ Doctoral School (DOKe), University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), Plaza Elhuyar 1, 20018 Donostia-San Sebastián, Spain, aselmanovi001@ikasle.ehu.eus

⁴ Department of Chemical and Environmental Engineering, University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), Plaza Europa 1, 20018 Donostia- San Sebastian, Spain, renealexander.herrera@ehu.eus

* Corresponding author

Miswak (*Salvadora persica*) has been widely researched for its use in oral hygiene, valued for its antimicrobial and therapeutic properties (Nordin et al., 2020). Although its use has primarily been limited to dental care, the rich chemical profile of miswak suggests broader potential (El-Sherbiny et al., 2023). This preliminary study aimed to explore the functional properties of miswak wood extractives to assess their potential for alternative applications in the building sector. Miswak wood was subjected to ultrasound-assisted extraction using an ethanol:water (90:10) solvent system. The extractives were analysed for total phenolic and flavonoid content, antioxidant activity (DPPH assay), and antimicrobial properties against selected bacterial strains. Furthermore, the extractives were exposed to controlled UV irradiation, and changes in their chemical profile were evaluated using FTIR spectroscopy. The extractives showed significant inhibitory activity against Gram-positive bacteria (*S. aureus*, *S. epidermidis*) and yeasts (*C. albicans*, *C. glabrata*), with lower activity observed against the Gram-negative bacteria *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa*, as well as *S. pyogenes*. These organisms represent a clinically relevant and microbiologically diverse test panel. Additionally, extractives exhibited antioxidant activity with positive correlations between total phenolic and flavonoid content. UV-induced changes in the chemical profile and antioxidant potential suggested possible light-induced transformations, and the need for further research on miswak extractives as potential UV filters. Given their antibacterial and antioxidant properties, the extractives may be explored as natural preservatives or bio-based protective solutions. The “green” extraction method used in this study offers an efficient and sustainable way to obtain miswak extractives without reducing their bioactivity. These findings highlight multifunctional bioactivity of miswak extractives and support their potential in material science.

Keywords: extractives, miswak, wood, spectroscopy, renewable materials

Acknowledgment: Authors acknowledge the Slovenian Research and Innovation Agency for co-financing the infrastructural program IO-0035 and research program WoBu. Dr. Pajerski further acknowledges the Slovenian Research and Innovation Agency for co-financing N2-0410.